

Factors Influencing Thresher Uptake: A Study of Agricultural Mechanization Research and Adaptation in Kenya

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Received: 10.04.2025 | Accepted: 17.05.2025 | Published: 05.07.2025

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15814944](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15814944)

Abstract

Original Research Article

Agricultural research organizations in developing countries are mandated by the governments in their respective countries to adapt technologies to the environmental conditions taking into consideration farmers' interests. Dissemination of these technologies by the research organizations should develop awareness among the farmers, which then leads to the adoption of the technology. Monitoring and evaluation of the adoption needs to be done to assess the progress of adoption and make adjustments where necessary. The general objective of the study was to establish the uptake of adapted threshers disseminated by the Agricultural Mechanization Research Institute in grain growing areas of Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards of Tharaka South Sub-County, Kenya. The specific objectives of the study were: (1) to determine the numerical progression of multi-crop threshers; and (2) to assess the preference of thresher usage against alternatives. The study was confined to the threshing of pulses using multi-crop threshing machines of 7.5 horsepower engines and smaller in Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards in November 2024. The study adopted an overview approach to capture several issues that would be useful in drawing accurate conclusions. Purposive sampling of Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards was informed by the first launching of the multi-crop threshing machine. A mixed-method approach using both secondary and primary data was used in November 2024. Interviews were conducted to collect data on participants' accounts among other details. The presentation of data was done with the use of bar graphs. The study concluded that awareness of the multi-crop threshing machine was first realized in 2020 in Tharaka Nithi County and since then, there had been a steady increase in the number of threshing machines in the area of study. The study also concluded that the users of the threshing machines were aware of its performance and benefits resulting from its use as compared to threshing using manual methods. The study recommends that AMR to address the following: a participatory approach in the designing of the threshing machines to adapt to the targeted geographic conditions; packaging dissemination contents to include demonstrations of operation for safe and efficient extraction of grain for seed and food use; and engagement of community leaders to partner in the adoption of threshing machines to increase the likelihood of adoption. All these will impact the livelihoods of the inhabitants of Tharaka Nithi through the alleviation of poverty and ensuring food security for the country in the long run.

Keywords: Adapt, Dissemination, Technology, Technology adoption, Uptake.

Citation: Lang'at, W. K., Wanjala, N. W., & Kipruto, K. K. (2025). Factors influencing thresher uptake: A study of agricultural mechanization research and adaptation in Kenya. *SSR Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(7), 1-15.

BACKGROUND

Throughout the world, agricultural research institutions have successfully supported farmers through the introduction of technological innovations in response to environmental and socio-economic challenges. This is a strategic approach that entails adapting agriculture to current and possible future challenges through research and development. Thereafter, the new technologies are disseminated to the public for uptake and adoption.

Technology is a broad term representing the knowledge of how to effectively use a product, process, or service (*know-*

how), how to conduct or control a manufacturing activity (*practice, process, or production technology*) (Schramm, 2017). Uptake is defined as the rate or act of accepting something (Angus & Maurice, 2011). Adoption commonly refers to the decision to use a new technology or practice by economic units regularly (Abera, 2008).

Many issues shape small-scale farmers' adoption of new technologies. Awareness (and subsequent adoption) of these technologies by farmers depends heavily upon several factors related to the farmer and the farming environment (Mashi *et al.*, 2022). The level of information reaching the farmer, perceived effectiveness of the

technology to the individual farmer and all the infrastructure and other capital resources required for the usage of the technology are altogether affecting the adoption process (Dissanayake *et al.*, 2022).

The Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO) is a public research organization. Within KALRO is the Agricultural Mechanization Research Institute (AMRI) whose basic function is to generate and disseminate agricultural mechanization technologies and innovations across the crops and livestock value chains in Kenya. One of the technologies developed and disseminated by AMRI is the post-harvest handling of pulses by threshing using the multi-crop threshing machine. AMRI adapts technologies to suit the local settings and to make an impact in the end-users' lives. The introduction of the multi-crop threshing machine is one of the modern technologies in agriculture in Kenya. Pattison *et al.*, (2023) describe threshing as the removal of the husk and other non-edible parts of the seed head before the seed is winnowed and ground. There are four kinds of threshing principles including impact, rubbing, combing and grinding, with four types of contact models between grain and threshing components having been constructed correspondingly (Fu *et al.*, 2018).

Before the development of this technology, the task characteristics of threshing and cleaning of pulses were done traditionally. It entailed the following: use of manual labour with beating sticks for threshing and natural wind to remove chaff; indefinite duration of threshing due to unreliable source of labour and weather; the need for large space outdoors; incomplete separation of grain from the crop; damaged grains due to bruises sustained from beating, thereby rendering them unfit for use as seed and they had a shortened shelf-life; spillage of some grains to the vicinity of the threshing area leading to contamination and reduction of grain quantity; and finally it was discriminative since the activity could not be performed by most gender. This cumbersome and wasteful process was

set to be replaced by the introduction of a multi-crop threshing machine.

The adapted multi-crop threshing machine provides the farmer with the following technology characteristics: ease of ferrying machine to and from the site; threshing of a variety of crops; shorter duration of threshing; working within a small space; the use of either gasoline or electricity; achieving a high level of separation of grain from crop; incurring very minimal damage to grain/seed; incurring minimal spillage, hence high standards of hygiene; operated by all gender (male, female, elderly, Persons With Disability); and operated by one person (the operator). All these features address the challenges faced in the traditional methods of threshing.

AMRI rolled out its first multi-crop threshing machines in the year 2020. Since then, the exercise has been conducted in various counties all over Kenya, thereby creating a socio-economic impact in the communities that adopted it. Long term contact farmers were engaged to assist the Institute on a long term evaluation programme to determine various efficiencies, lifespan, ergonomics, and end-user appeal, amongst other parameters. The Counties involved are: Busia, Uasin Gishu, Bungoma, Kitui, Marsabit and Machakos (on-station).

Tharaka Nithi County is also one of the Counties that actively participated in the multi-crop threshing program in its Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards, Figure 1. The majority of residents in the region are small-scale farmers with an average landholding of two acres (0.8 ha). According to KFSSG (2024), the main crops grown in the county are maize, millet, pigeon peas, green grams, sorghum and cowpeas across all livelihood zones. Maize, millet, pigeon peas are most produced in the mixed farming livelihood zone for food while green grams, sorghum and cowpeas take precedence in the marginal mixed farming zone. To fully exploit the potential of Tharaka Nithi County in providing food, mechanization of post-harvest handling must be embraced.

Figure 1: Tharaka Nithi County

Source: Tharaka Nithi County Government (TNCG), 2019.

Objective:

The general objective was to assess the uptake of adapted threshers disseminated by the Agricultural Mechanization Research Institute in grain growing areas of Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards of Tharaka South Sub-County, Kenya.

Specific Objectives:

The specific objectives were:

1. To determine the multi-crop thresher progression.
2. To assess the preference of multi-crop thresher usage against alternatives.

Scope:

The study was confined to threshing pulses using crop threshers with 7.5 horsepower engines that were small enough to be transported by motorbike from village to village in Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards in November 2024.

Justification:

Occasional conflicts along Tharaka Nithi County's borders will be reduced since small farmers residing in these areas shall embrace more financially rewarding ventures made easy through agricultural mechanization. The determination of the extent to which AMRI's strategies of introducing agricultural mechanization innovations such as multi-crop threshing machines is important in the development and implementation of technology dissemination strategies, hence improvement of farmers' livelihoods.

METHODOLOGY:

Understanding how multi-crop thresher evolves and how it compares to other harvesting efforts is crucial. This study aimed to: 1. Determine the progression of multi-crop thresher populations; and 2. Assess user preferences for multi-crop threshers versus alternative options. An overview of the target areas about the interactions of the farmers and the machine was undertaken. This is because it could answer important questions about technology use by finding out what crops farmers grew, type of crop, major constraints in specific value chains, cost of threshing, drudgery, and the economic benefits.

The purposive selection of Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards, Figure 2, as the location of the study was done since these are the two areas where AMR conducted sensitization in the year 2020. Thereafter, the study used a mixed-method approach involving secondary data collection and survey tool to study the awareness and adoption of multi-crop threshing machines in the target area. Secondary data was used to establish the number of threshing machines in the study area in the year 2020.

Primary data collection was conducted in November 2024 through interviews which were used to gather information from individuals face to face and by phone, using predetermined questions from Tharaka South thresher density. The interviews were recorded and transcribed. Interviews were used to document participants' accounts, perceptions of, or stories about their attitudes toward and responses to certain situations or phenomena. Both descriptive and analytical statistics were used to analyse the data and displayed in bar graphs. The findings were discussed thereafter.

Figure 2: Nkondi, Marimanti and Chiakariga wards of Tharaka Nithi County

Source: Tharaka Nithi County Government (TNCG), 2019.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Tharaka Nithi is divided into North, South and Central. Marimanti is the headquarters of Tharaka Nithi with a population of 38,914 (KEBS), North Tharaka, 36,904 and South Tharaka 25,114. Tharaka North is headquartered at Marimanti - South at Chiakariga, North at Gatunga. The main economic activities are farming, pastoralism, sand harvesting and quarrying (Gikunda, 2015). All regions range from semi-arid to arid, so they grow dry-land crops. The drivers of food and nutrition insecurity in the region includes the erratic performance of the long rains, high food prices, high cost of farm inputs, crop failures, crop pests, livestock diseases and limiting

water access (TNC, 2024). Tharaka-Nithi is faced with agricultural mechanization needs due to drudgery, efficiency and lack of labour during their crop production along their value chains. The crops grown are green grams, sorghum, maize, cow peas, millet, etc. The most labour demanding task along the value chain is post-harvest handling.

AMRI singled out threshing as a major problem in grain production in Tharaka Nithi and introduced a multi-crop thresher through an outreach program in the year 2020. It is now four years later AMRI is reviewing the impact of the machine on the populace production.

Though a survey, only 22.2 % responded from Marimanti, and the rest from Chiakariga, Figure 3.

Figure 3: Residence of Respondents

Since its establishment, KALRO has been participating in National and County exhibitions under various themes. AMRI is featured in most of these events. Therein, KALRO aims to create awareness among the public of the products and services it offers. Thereafter, the public adopts the disseminated technologies. The process of adopting an innovation, however, shows that awareness is a prerequisite which needs to be understood before adoption can be addressed (Claudy *et al.*, 2010).

According to Melesse (2018), farmers with frequent contacts with the extension services were said to be more liable to adopt novel technologies than farmers who had less frequent contacts.

The study sought to establish the extent to which the public was aware of KALRO's existence, Figure 4. The survey revealed that all the respondents (100%) were aware of AMRI.

Figure 4: Awareness of existence of KALRO-AMRI

The study sought to establish the extent to which the public was aware of AMRI's existence and the services it offers, Figure 5.

The survey showed that all the respondents who were aware of the existence of AMRI, responded as follows:

66.7% believed that AMRI conducted research on Agricultural Mechanization while the rest (33.3%) stated that it conducted research on crops. None of the respondents stated research on either livestock or had no idea what AMRI engaged in.

Figure 5: Awareness of KALRO – AMRI Activities

There are two main livelihood zones in Tharaka-Nithi, namely; Marginal Mixed Farming (MMF), and Mixed Farming (MF). Agriculture (crop and livestock production) is the main occupation for the households in the livelihood zones. In the Mixed Farming livelihood

zone, crop production heavily relies on seasonal rain (TNC, 2024). The study sought to establish the number of respondents who engaged in farming, Figure 6. The findings revealed that 100% of the respondents were farmers.

Figure 6: Number of respondents who are farmers.

The majority of residents in the region are small-scale farmers with an average landholding of two acres. The key food staples consumed per livelihood are in Mixed farming, maize, millet, beans and cowpeas, while in the Marginal mixed farming, millet and cowpeas (TNC, 2024). Feder *et al.*, (1985), stated that technologies such as mechanization or the involvement of machinery will cause elevated costs which will require larger cultivation extents

to become profitable. This explains why more farmers with more acreage are seen to own more machines than those with smaller land area. The study wanted to establish the size of land each of the respondents had under crops, Figure 7. The findings were that 33.3% of the respondents had planted crops in an area covering less than 2 acres, 22.2% on approximately 2 acres, while the rest was over 2 acres.

Figure 7: Size of the farmers' land under crops.

The main crops grown in the county are maize, millet, pigeon peas, green grams, sorghum and cowpeas across all livelihood zones. Maize, millet, pigeon peas are most produced in the mixed farming livelihood zone for food while green grams, sorghum and cowpeas take precedence in the marginal mixed farming zone. Green grams crop is largely produced for sale and contribute only 8 percent to households' food needs (TNC, 2024).

The crops which are least grown may be attributed to the season in the county – whether it is currently short/long rains, hence scarcity of the commodity, necessitating importation of crops such as maize from neighbouring

counties.

The study sought to establish the types of crops grown by the respondents, Figure 8. Some respondents grew either one, two or several crops. The response was as follows: green grams was grown by 25% of respondents, Cowpeas by 9.4%, Millet by 18.8%, Pigeon peas by 9.4%, Sorghum by 18.8%, Maize by 15.6%, Beans by 3.1% and finally none of the respondents grew Soya beans.

Dogra & Singh (2018), state that due to lack of assured markets, farmers are reluctant to adopt diversification techniques and lack of mechanization of various farming operations.

Figure 8: Type of crops grown by the farmers in Chiakariga and Marimanti.

Before the introduction of the thresher to the region, most of the post-harvest handling were done manually, and most of the people were seeing it for the first time. AMRI disseminated crop threshing technology by use of machine in the year 2020. It not only delivered the machines to both Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards, but also performed demonstrations there.

The study sought to establish at when the farmers got to know of the existence of the multi-crop threshing machine, Figure 9. The findings revealed that 22.2% of respondents became aware of the use of a threshing machine before the year 2020, 55.6% in the year 2020 and 22.2% after the year 2020.

Figure 9: Time of awareness of the use of threshing machine.

Gajbhiye *et al.*, (2016) describe the various methods of threshing as follows: hand threshing entails striking the sheaves of the crops spread over threshing floor with a flail

or stick; threshing with animals which requires availability of draught animals which tread over 30cm thick layer of sheaves (also known as treading-out) or running a tractor

twice over sheaves of harvested and dried crops that are spread in layers on a circular threshing floor 15-18m in diameter; threshing with hand driven machines like Olped thresher which is basically used for threshing of paddy; and threshing with motorized thresher or threshers operated by tractor power.

The researcher wanted to establish the method currently used by the respondents in threshing their crops, Figure 10. The findings revealed that 88.9% of the respondents used threshing machines while 11.1% manually threshed their crops.

Even though most farmers desire to thresh their crops using threshing machines, some factors do limit them. Stanly *et al.*, (2020) states that the scarcity of machinery and non-availability of small size machinery makes the job difficult in hills – such as Tharaka-Nithi. This, therefore forces farmers in the hilly regions to use conventional methods like hand beating, and animal feet trampling for threshing crops. Another reason would be that in instances where farmers use own seed for next seasons’ planting, they may have the fear that using threshing machines would damage the seeds hence affecting their viability.

Figure 10: Method used by farmers to thresh their crops.

The farmer’s opinion was sort with regard to the number of threshing machine owners in existence in Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards in the year 2024, Figure 11. The majority of the respondents (44.4%) estimated that there

existed 3 to 5 threshing machines in the area of study. 11.1% were not sure how many there were in the same area.

Figure 11: Estimated number of threshing machines currently existing in the respondents’ ward.

The farmers’ opinion was sort with regard to the number of threshing machine owners in existence in Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards in the year 2021, Figure 12. The

findings revealed that most respondents thought that there existed approximately 4 threshing machines in the year 2021.

Figure 12: Estimated number of threshing machine owners in Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards in 2021.

The farmer's opinion was sort with regard to the number of threshing machine owners in existence in Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards in the year 2022, Figure 13. The findings revealed that majority of the respondents (77.7%) estimated that 4 to 5 threshing machines exited in the area

of study. This indicated a slight increase in the number of machines compared to the previous year. This could be attributed to the continued awareness of the existence of the technology hence more adoption of the same by farmers.

Figure 13: Estimated number of threshing machine owners in Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards in 2022.

The study sought the farmers' opinion with regard to the number of threshing machine owners in existence in Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards in the year 2023, Figure 14. The findings revealed that there was a strong affirmation of the existence of approximately 5 threshers in Marimanti and Chiakariga Wards. Compared to when

the threshers were introduced, this is a higher figure. There hadn't been any awareness conducted by KALRO, therefore the most likely explanation for this increase is that the farmers influenced each other to adopt this technology.

Figure 14: Estimated number of threshing machine owners in Chiakariga and Marimanti Wards in 2023.

Time is a limited resource. The same for storage space in a farm setup. Stanly *et al.*, (2020) state that since turnaround time between pulse crops is less - pulse crops are fast growing and short duration crops it becomes essential that the crops are threshed timely. This will free the farmer, his time and the storage structures to prepare and hold the next season's batch of crop. The farmer may even sell this crop to make money plough it back as capital

to the next farming activity.

The opinion of farmer was sort with regard to the duration it took to thresh a bag of green grams manually, Figure 15. 66.7% stated that it took less than 3 days, 33.3% indicated that it took 3 days, while none said it would exceed 3 days. This could be attributed to lack of capital to pay wages for the labour, lack of reliable labour, drudgery and poor weather conditions.

Figure 15: Duration of threshing a bag of green grams manually.

Dogra & Singh (2018), stated that threshing of pulses can save precious labour and time as compared to traditional methods, and that tests showed favorable results compared to traditional methods due to lesser losses and high degree of leaning efficiency. The study sought the farmers' opinion with regard to the duration it took them to thresh a bag of green grams using a threshing machine, Figure 16. 22.2% indicated that it took 3 to 5 minutes, 44.4% agreed

that it took 6 to 8 minutes, while the rest stated that it took more than 8 minutes. Generally, it was clear that, depending on the condition of the crop and the operation of the machine, a bag of green grams could be threshed from 3 to 8 minutes. This was way faster than using manual methods to thresh. The variations in time had to do with operator skills and crop condition.

Figure 16: Duration of threshing a bag of green grams using a threshing machine.

The cost of labour to perform an operation in a locality is dependent on the demand and supply of the labour for a given task. Since all the respondents were in the same area, they were all in agreement on the cost of threshing a bag of green grams with the threshing machine.

The study sought the farmers' opinion with regard to the cost of threshing a bag of green grams using a threshing machine, Figure 17. All respondents agreed that it cost Kshs. 300.

Figure 17: Cost of threshing a bag of green grams with a threshing machine.

Dissanayake *et al.*, (2022), discussed the main factors influencing technology adoption in agriculture sector under three categories: 1. Factors related to the user; 2. Factors related to the technology; and 3. Institutional factors. Stanly *et al.*, (2020) states that conventional methods of threshing are tiresome, time consuming and labour intensive, results in high seed damage and threshing

losses. According to Yokamo (2020), the technology developer should incorporate the need and perceptions of farmers during technology design and development; this will enhance the adoption of the technology more easily. The study sought to know the farmers' preferred method of threshing. All the respondents preferred threshing by use of machine, Figure 18.

Figure 18: Preferred method of threshing crops.

CONCLUSION

Majority of the respondents (55.6%) became aware of the use of threshing machines in the year 2020 when KALRO carried out sensitization in Tharaka Nithi County on the use of threshing machines. A large number of respondents (44.4%) estimated that a maximum of 5 machines existed at that moment in Marimanti and Chiakariga Wards combined. There was a steady increase in the number of threshing machines in the past three years since 2021 - a feat attributed to AMR. From AMR's records, 2 multi-crop threshing machines were introduced in Marimanti and Chiakariga Wards - one made by AMR and a commercial one.

Although all the respondents preferred using a threshing machine, a few still used manual methods. Majority of the respondents agree that it takes approximately less than three days to thresh a bag of green grams using manual methods while it took a shorter time of 6 to 8 minutes to thresh the same using a threshing machine at a cost of Kshs. 300 per bag.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Firstly, there is need to analyze the topographic challenges faced by farmers in the hilly areas of Tharaka

Nithi so as to inform the design process for appropriate adaptation of agricultural machinery. There is need to provide farmers with information on how to ensure safe separation of grain that they intend to use as seed.

Secondly, there is need for continued building of awareness amongst farmers on the use of threshing machines so as to increase its adoption.

Thirdly, Field and Extension Service providers could co-opt influential farmers in the communities to aid in disseminating such technologies since they are more believable by members of their community.

Fourthly, there is need to sensitize and demonstrate to farmers on the assured benefits of timeliness of operations when they use threshing machines. In addition, the importance of attaining the right moisture so as to achieve maximum separation of grain from crop within a short time.

Fifthly, there is need to sensitize and demonstrate to farmers how to get optimum performance of a threshing machine and maximum separation of grain from crop.

Finally, farmers' desire to adopt technology should be capitalized to ensure new technologies are developed and disseminated in as short a time as possible. This will not only alleviate poverty but it will ensure food security for the country in the long run.

APPENDIX I: Questionnaire:

Title: Uptake of Post-harvest Technologies: The Case of Agricultural Mechanization and Adaptation of Threshers in Kenya.

Which Ward do you come from?

Chiakariga

Marimanti

Have you heard of the Agricultural Mechanization Research Institute-Katumani (KALRO)?

Yes

No

If Yes in 2 above, what do you know about KALRO-AMRI?

Research on Agricultural Mechanization

Research on Livestock

Research on Crops

No idea

Are you a farmer?

Yes

No

What size of your land is under crops?

Below 2 acres

Approximately 2 acres

Over 2 acres

Which crops do you grow?

Green grams

Cow Peas

Millet

Pigeon Peas

Sorghum

Maize

Beans

Soya Beans

When did you get knowledge of using a threshing machine?

Before the year 2020

In the year 2020

After the year 2020

How do you thresh your crops?

Manually

Machine

How many threshers would you estimate to be available within your Ward today?

3 to 5

6 to 8

More than 8

I don't know

How many machine owners could you count by 2021?

1

2

3

4

5

How many machine owners could you count by 2022?

1

2

3

4

5

How many machine owners could you count by 2023?

1

2

3

4

5

- How long does it take to thresh a bag of green grams manually?
- Less than 3 days
 - 3 days
 - More than 3 days
- How long does it take to thresh a bag of green grams using a threshing machine?
- 3 to 5 minutes
 - 6 to 8 minutes
 - More than 8 minutes
- How much does it cost to thresh a bag of green grams with a threshing machine?
- Kshs. 900
 - Kshs. 600
 - Kshs. 300
- Which method would you prefer when threshing?
- Manual
 - Machine

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